

Characterization of Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage with Hot Push Pull Test: what can be learnt from geochemical / reactive transport modelling? (PUSH-IT project)

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ABSTRACT

The PUSH-IT project explores full-scale applications of medium to high temperature (50-90°C) Underground Thermal Energy Storage (UTES) across six diverse European sites using three distinct storage technologies. This study presents the preliminary findings from the Delft site, where Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage (ATES) technology is being implemented. Biogeochemical experiments are also being conducted to assess how the increase of temperature affects biogeochemical process and microbial activity (see companion abstract Watkinson et al., EGC 2025).

Hot push and pull tests (HPPT) are conducted to characterize the hydraulic, thermal and geochemical properties of poorly consolidated aquifers located at depths between 120 m to 180 m (Delft, NL). The HPPT consists of a few cycles with the following steps: pumping of a few hundred cubic meters of "cold" fluid; heating of the fluid in a tank at the surface; addition of tracers; reinjection of the hot fluid in the same aquifer; relaxation of the system; pumping of the stored hot water and water quality analysis to check the variations of chemical compositions.

The data collected during the HPPT is used to feed reactive transport models. Marthe-PHREEQC is used to account for thermal exchanges and heat transport in the porous media, in addition to water-rock interactions. This approach enables a comprehensive evaluation of how temperature influences the geochemical processes, particularly precipitation and dissolution reactions near the well, and water quality.

These results provide important insights into the thermal and geochemical dynamics of high-temperature heat storage systems, providing valuable data to limit adverse impacts and/or design water treatment to control such impacts to improve the use of ATEs technology across Europe.

1. INTRODUCTION

Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage (ATES) is a promising technology for seasonal heat storage, enabling the efficient reuse of thermal energy in district heating and cooling systems (Fleuchaus et al., 2018; Brown et al., 2024; Fry et al., 2024; Marojević et al., 2025). By injecting and extracting heated water into and from underground aquifers, ATEs can significantly reduce reliance on conventional energy sources and enhance the sustainability of urban heating infrastructure. However, one of the key challenges associated with ATEs is the management of the potential for biogeochemical alterations in the reservoir, particularly mineral precipitation, which can lead to well clogging and reduced system efficiency.

Among the most critical geochemical processes affecting ATEs performance is the precipitation of carbonate minerals, primarily calcite (CaCO₃). The increase in temperature during warm water injection shifts the equilibrium of carbonate chemistry, often leading to supersaturation and subsequent precipitation. Over time, this process can alter the porosity and permeability of the aquifer, particularly near the well screen, potentially impairing system performance. Previous studies have documented similar clogging phenomena in other geothermal and ATEs systems (Song et al., 2020; Markó et al., 2024; Masuda et al., 2025), emphasizing the need for predictive modelling and mitigation strategies.

In this study, we perform reactive transport modelling of a push-pull test conducted in a sandy aquifer at TU Delft to evaluate the extent of carbonate precipitation under ATEs conditions. The simulations allow assessing mineral saturation dynamics during injection, storage, and extraction phases. In addition, we explore potential mitigation strategies, specifically the injection of water equilibrated with a $p\text{CO}_2$, to determine whether this approach can effectively suppress carbonate precipitation while minimizing undesirable secondary reactions such as aluminosilicate dissolution. By comparing our simulation results with existing literature and discussing their implications for ATEs design, we aim to provide valuable insights into optimizing long-term system performance and preventing clogging-related failures.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Site characteristics

The ATEs system under study is located on the TU Delft technology campus in the Netherlands. The area's subsol is structured into three superimposed aquifers. The third aquifer, the Maassluis formation (formed during the Pleistocene, i.e. 2.5 million years ago), is located between 123- and 184-meters depth. It is characterized by 4 alternating layers of fine to moderately coarse sand, interspersed with 3 levels of clay and silt (Figure 1). The effective thickness of these 4 sub-reservoirs is in the order of ten to twenty meters. Clay interfaces, each around 2 m thick, isolate each of the compartments. Analyses of water composition from the 4 reservoirs seem to confirm the low mass transfers between reservoirs. The water temperature in these reservoirs is around 14°C. The overall porosity is 28%.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of reservoir structure and properties at the TU Delft site. K: hydraulic conductivity

2.2 Hot push pull tests

Push-Pull tests on the site will start in summer 2025. They consist of a succession of hot water injection phases followed by so-called relaxation periods. During the injection phase, water heated to around 90°C is injected into the aquifer; the relaxation phase

corresponds to the temporary stop of injection, enabling to observe how the aquifer interacts with the stored water, particularly in terms of geochemical reactions and heat dissipation. A possible third phase can be integrated, consisting of re-pumping the injected water to analyze the fluid's physico-chemical evolution.

2.3 Modelling strategy

Reactive transport modelling was performed using the transport code MARTHE (Thiery et al., 2018) coupled with the geochemical speciation code PHREEQC (Parkhurst and Appelo, 2013), which simulates water-rock interactions. This coupling enables the model to account for both chemical reactions and thermal exchanges induced by the operating cycles of the Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage (ATEs) system. The thermodynamic database THERMODDEM (Blanc et al., 2012) was used for geochemical calculations.

Table 1: Properties and composition of the water in the aquifer layers and of the injected water. Concentration in mol/L. Campaign realized in October 2024.

Layer	1	2	3	4	Injected Solution
Temperature (°C)	14	14	14	14	90
pH	6.78	6.88	6.88	7.43	6.56
Al	1.62E-03	1.19E-03	1.05E-03	3.96E-04	1.02E-03
Ar	1.68E-05	1.52E-04	6.77E-05	2.72E-05	4.60E-05
B	2.41E-05	2.31E-05	3.42E-05	6.38E-05	4.06E-05
Ba	2.11E-06	2.18E-06	2.84E-06	1.82E-06	2.12E-06
Br	1.38E-04	1.38E-04	1.50E-04	2.13E-04	1.68E-04
CO ₃ ⁻²	8.63E-03	6.73E-03	5.81E-03	1.80E-03	5.43E-03
CH ₄	2.11E-04	4.98E-05	4.01E-05	4.14E-07	2.15E-05
Ca	1.02E-02	9.57E-03	1.17E-02	1.04E-02	1.04E-02
Cl	9.20E-02	9.34E-02	1.04E-01	1.47E-01	1.15E-01
Fe	5.09E-05	2.12E-05	1.80E-05	2.08E-07	2.29E-05
K	4.75E-13	7.19E-13	9.98E-13	9.21E-12	3.91E-12
Li	8.65E-06	9.37E-06	9.65E-06	8.21E-06	8.73E-06
Mg	9.00E-03	8.48E-03	1.03E-02	9.34E-03	9.25E-03
Mn	2.55E-06	2.18E-06	2.73E-06	2.00E-06	2.32E-06
Mo	0.00E+00	6.46E-07	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	8.40E-08
NH ₄ ⁺	6.14E-04	6.00E-04	7.85E-04	1.00E-03	7.84E-04
Na	9.09E-02	6.93E-02	8.24E-02	7.39E-02	8.03E-02
P	1.52E-05	1.23E-05	8.07E-06	8.07E-06	1.10E-05
S	7.80E-04	4.68E-04	1.87E-03	7.49E-03	3.45E-03
Si	2.88E-07	3.49E-07	3.70E-07	7.74E-07	4.93E-07
Zn	0.00E+00	2.14E-07	3.21E-07	4.32E-08	7.60E-08

The model was designed as a two-dimensional (2D) radial cross-section, which provides an appropriate representation of fluid injection and displacement from a well in a homogeneous sandy aquifer. The computational domain extended 55 m radially and 234 m in thickness, encompassing four distinct aquifer layers separated by clay layers. The domain was discretized into 26 columns, 20 rows, and 35 vertical layers, resulting in approximately 18,000

computational cells. To capture the key hydrogeological processes, a refined vertical discretization was applied in the aquifer layers, whereas the clay layers were represented by coarser cells. The first and fourth aquifers, being the thickest, were discretized into six layers, while the second and third aquifers were divided into four layers each. The separating clay layers were represented by a single layer, except for the first 10 m of the upper and lower boundary clay formations, where a finer discretization was applied to improve the representation of heat dissipation.

The initial conditions assumed a uniform aquifer temperature of 14°C, with each aquifer layer's porewater in chemical equilibrium with the corresponding mineral composition. The mineralogy of the aquifer was homogeneous and consisted of quartz (35 mol/L of rock), calcite (1.11 mol/L), anorthite (4.45×10^{-1} mol/L), illite (1.12×10^{-1} mol/L), dolomite (2.06×10^{-1} mol/L), smectite (1.76×10^{-1} mol/L), and chlorite (3.44×10^{-2} mol/L). Boundary conditions were defined such that fluid injection occurred through the first cell of each aquifer layer, with permeability values assigned as shown in Figure 1. The clay layers were assumed to have very low permeability (1×10^{-2} m/day) and low porosity (0.01%), minimizing vertical fluid migration. The transport of water and heat was computed using an implicit finite-volume discretization based on the Integrated Finite Differences (IFD) method. Flow dynamics were governed by Darcy's law and the mass conservation equation, while heat transfer accounted for both convective and conductive mechanisms. During injection, heat transport was dominated by advection, whereas, in the relaxation phase, thermal diffusion governed the redistribution of heat within the aquifer.

The geochemical model considered both equilibrium and kinetic reactions. For reasons of calculation time, only the dissolution and precipitation of calcite, dolomite, and quartz were modelled. Previous batch calculations suggested that anorthite, smectite, and chlorite kinetics were negligible. The kinetic rate parameters were derived from the THERMODDEM database (Marty et al., 2015). To assess the impact of cyclic thermal storage on geochemical reactivity a push-pull test was simulated with two successive

injection-relaxation cycles of 48 hours each, totaling 96 hours of simulation. Each injection phase lasted 24 hours, followed by a 24-hour relaxation period. Injection was performed at a constant flow rate of 60 m³/h, using a heated mixture of water from the four aquifers at 90°C. The contribution of each aquifer to the injected fluid was 34%, 13%, 15%, and 38%, respectively, mirroring the composition of the production well. The water chemical compositions of each aquifer and the injected solution are reported in Table 1.

Additionally, a mitigation strategy was tested by simulating the injection of water equilibrated with 0.5 bar of CO₂. This pressure was selected based on batch equilibrium calculations: this CO₂ pressure allow maintaining the calcite saturation index at zero of the hot fluid, preventing the injection of a fluid supersaturated with respect to carbonates and thus their precipitation. The CO₂-enriched injection was performed under the same operational conditions as the standard push-pull test. However, the code does not account for degassing, so potential CO₂ exiting the aqueous phase and forming a gaseous phase was not considered in the simulations.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Thermal response after injection

The injection of hot water at 90°C significantly altered the temperature distribution within the aquifer. Figure 2 shows that the thermal front propagated radially outward from the injection well, with the temperature changes reaching approximately 45 m from the well after 96 hours of operation. During the relaxation phases (24–48 h and 72–96 h), no further injection occurred, and heat dissipation was observed. The surrounding aquifer, initially at 14°C, act as a heat sink, but heat transfer is slow, varying only by tenth of degrees in 24 h. The thermal profile at 48 h show only minor cooling near the well, indicating that the aquitard layers acted as a thermal barrier, limiting vertical heat dissipation. Energy dissipation occurred primarily within the first 3 meters of the upper and lower clay layers, highlighting their strong insulating properties. The interlayer clays show a temperature of a 55°C because of their confinement between the aquifers.

Figure 2: Temperature field following two injection/relaxation cycles at t=96h.

3.2 Chemical Response: Carbonate Precipitation and Dissolution

The most notable geochemical effect was the precipitation of calcite in the immediate vicinity of the injection well. After 96 hours of operation, calcite content reached a maximum of 1.15 mol/L of rock compared to the initial 1.1 mol/L, with the most significant precipitation occurring within the first meter of the well (Figure 3). This localized mineral buildup could potentially impact aquifer permeability and injectivity over time. A quick calculation shows that an increase of 0.05 mol/L of rock represents 1.85 cm³, i.e.

a 0.66% decrease in porosity compared to an initial value of 280 cm³/L of rock.

The spatial distribution of quartz dissolution after 96 hours of operation is illustrated in Figure 4. The values represent the change in quartz concentration (Δ Quartz) in mol/L of rock rather than the total amount present in each cell. The dissolution was most pronounced near the injection well, where elevated temperatures and fluid-rock interactions promoted silica undersaturation. Moving radially outward from the well, the intensity of quartz dissolution gradually decreased. This trend suggests that the injected solution is undersaturated with respect to quartz. Moreover, Dissolution process is accentuated by thermal effects and the advective transport of reactive fluids.

Figure 3: Calcite concentration following two injection/relaxation cycles at t=96h. Concentration is in mol/L of rock

Figure 4: Δ Quartz concentration following two injection/relaxation cycles at $t=96h$. Concentration is in mol/L of rock.

3.3 Thermal and Chemical Response with CO₂-Enriched Injection

The second simulation was conducted with an injected solution equilibrated with 0.5 bar of CO₂. This adjustment aimed to lower the pH and reduce calcite supersaturation. As consequences, the injected solution displayed 9.8 mmol/L of dissolved CO₂ against 5.4 mmol/L previously; and a pH of 6.01 against 6.56 previously (Table 1). Thermal response was no different from the previous simulations. Concerning the geochemistry however, the results indicate a significant

decrease in calcite precipitation near the well, preventing the strong accumulation observed in the baseline case (Figure 5). The color scale highlights a clear dissolution trend. The dissolution is most pronounced in the vicinity of the injection well, where the acidified fluid interacts with the carbonate matrix, enhancing mineral solubility. Moving radially outward, the extent of dissolution decreases as the CO₂-rich solution equilibrates with the surrounding formation water. The zoomed-in section further emphasizes the sharp dissolution front, indicating a strong geochemical response to CO₂ introduction near the well.

Figure 5: Calcite concentration after 96h of operation with CO₂-enriched solution. Concentration is in mol/L of rock

Figure 6: Δ Quartz concentration after 96h of operation with CO₂-enriched solution. Concentration is in mol/L of rock

Figure 6 presents the evolution of quartz dissolution (Δ Quartz) after the injection of CO₂-enriched water. The dissolution pattern remains radially distributed from the injection well, consistent with the previous calcite evolution. However, compared to the simulation without CO₂, the dissolution intensity is significantly greater, particularly in the near-well region. The simulation highlights higher dissolution rates in the immediate vicinity of the injection point, likely due to increased acidification from CO₂ dissolution. The zoomed-in section further emphasizes the dissolution gradients, showing a progressive decrease in intensity moving outward. These results suggest that CO₂ introduction not only affects carbonate dissolution but also influences silicate mineral stability. Although quartz dissolution increased with the addition of CO₂, it remains negligible compared to the amount of mineral present in the aquifer.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Thermal Response of the Aquifer and the Role of the Clay Interface

The thermal evolution of the aquifer following high temperature water injection highlights the influence of the surrounding geological formations in regulating heat transfer. The advection causes thermal convection to drive the temperature field. The presence of a clay interface plays a crucial role in diffusing thermal energy, acting as a buffer that slows down vertical heat transfer and favor horizontal thermal convection. Preliminary calculations indicate that the return to baseline temperatures may take several months, emphasizing the slow thermal inertia of the system. At this point, it is not possible to assess on the suitability of the aquifer for energy storage application because of the short duration of the model and the absence of experimental data. The goal for thermal storage aquifer is to be able to recover the stored thermal energy from previous injections by pumping, allowing efficient heat extraction for heating purposes. Studies such as Heldt et al. (2021), Hoffmann et al. (2021) and Miotliński and

Dillon (2021) suggest that convective mixing or permeability anisotropy accelerate temperature equilibration. Heldt et al. (2021) shows that injection of a 70°C solution into a subsurface sandy aquifer took about 2.5 months to return to baseline temperatures. At the contrary Yapparova et al. (2014) show that even 120 days after injection, a 70°C plume could be detected in a gravel aquifer delimited by clay layers suggesting slow thermal energy transfer into their aquifer. Our study require more experimental data and simulations over longer period of time assess the thermal behavior of the aquifer.

4.1 Geochemistry and Carbonate Scaling Patterns

Carbonate scaling (precipitation) is a widely observed phenomenon in geothermal activities (Zhang et al., 2001; Boch et al., 2017). Zhang et al. (2001) shows that the nucleation rate increases with supersaturation, following classical nucleation theory. Their study shows that precipitation follows a power-law dependence on supersaturation as introduced by Palandri and Kharaka (2004) and used in Marty et al. (2015) kinetic database in the form:

$$R = k(\Omega - 1)^n \quad 1$$

Where k is the kinetic constant and Ω is the saturation ratio of the mineral. With a saturation index (SI) of 0.5 in the injected solution (Marion (2001) and Benezeth et al. (2013)), calcite scaling will naturally be formed and enhanced because of advection-dominated transport. In absence of on-site results in this study, it is not possible to concur whether calcite precipitation follows a kinetic or thermodynamic approach is more reliable for calcite reactivity.

The radial distribution of calcite scaling demonstrates a clear spatial gradient of mineral precipitation, with the highest concentration of calcite forming near the injection well and progressively decreasing with radial distance. These findings align with key observations by Arnorsson et al. (2007) who highlighted the

temperature-dependent nature of mineral precipitation, particularly calcite. Our observation of a radial decrease in precipitation supports their theoretical models of geochemical alteration in reservoir environments. These findings align as well with the temperature field of the simulation. Rohmen et al. (2019) suggested that elevated temperatures can significantly accelerate mineral transformation processes. Our simulation corroborates this hypothesis, showing how thermal gradients induce complex geochemical reactions that are spatially heterogeneous.

However, our studies diverge from studies such as Na et al. (2015 or Xu et al (2012) highlighting the importance of reservoir lithology in geochemical processes. The sandy aquifer context distinguishes our research. While many geothermal studies focus on fractured or carbonate reservoirs, our work provides valuable insights into sedimentary environments. The precipitation pattern we observed suggests that sedimentary characteristics significantly influence mineral transformation processes, a finding that could have broader implications for geothermal reservoir management.

4.3 Role of CO₂ in chemical response

The simulated carbonate scaling patterns exhibit both alignments and divergences when compared to existing studies on CO₂-enriched water injection in deep aquifers. Regarding carbonate scaling, the simulation confirms the well-documented phenomenon of calcite dissolution near the injection well, driven by acidification from CO₂ dissolution. When equilibrated with gaseous CO₂ at 0.5 bars, calcite SI is closed to 0 but pH is also more acidic. When it comes into contact with the rock mineralogy it naturally induced mineral dissolution due to its more acidic pH. This pattern aligns with studies that have demonstrated enhanced carbonate dissolution under similar injection conditions (Na et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2015; Kim and Santamarina, 2015). However, the radial extent and intensity of dissolution in our model suggest a potentially more localized effect compared to some field-scale observations, where preferential flow paths or heterogeneous mineral distributions can lead to uneven dissolution fronts.

Furthermore, the evolution of Δ Quartz highlights an increased dissolution intensity compared to the previous non-CO₂ scenario, although quartz dissolution remains not significant. Acidification from CO₂-enriched brine can enhance the dissolution of anorthite, chlorite and clays (illite and smectite) as displayed by their respective SI of -0.29, -1.00, -0.25 and -0.42. This would not only alter aquifer porosity but also release Fe, Al, and other trace metals into the water. This process has been observed in several CO₂ storage and geothermal projects (Jang et al., 2022; Ilgen and Cygan, 2016), where silicate dissolution contributes to secondary mineral precipitation downstream. The matter is of importance as Fe and Al released from dissolving aluminosilicates may pose water quality concerns and facilitate secondary precipitation

reactions. For instance, Fe²⁺ could oxidize and precipitate as Fe(III) oxides or hydroxides, potentially forming new scaling issues in wells or pipes.

Overall, although a CO₂-enriched brine maintains injectivity, long-term effects must be considered. Over time, excessive carbonate dissolution could alter aquifer properties, potentially leading to unintended permeability changes or mechanical instability.

5. CONCLUSION

This study provides a comprehensive investigation of geochemical and thermal responses during high-temperature brine injection in a multilayered sandy aquifer. Our key findings provide understanding into the complex interactions between thermal energy storage and mineral transformation processes:

- The injection of 90°C brine demonstrated a slow vertical thermal transfer, suggesting that clay interfaces act as thermal barriers. The thermal front propagated radially, extending approximately 45 m from the injection well after 96 hours.
- The simulation revealed a distinct radial gradient of calcite precipitation, with the highest concentration occurring within the first meter of the injection well. This localized mineral buildup could potentially impact aquifer permeability and injectivity over time, underscoring the importance of predictive geochemical modeling. Estimates suggest that the calcite precipitation induced 0.66 % of porosity decrease.
- The injection of CO₂-equilibrated water demonstrated an effective approach to mitigating calcite scaling. By lowering the pH and reducing carbonate supersaturation, the CO₂-enriched solution prevented significant mineral precipitation and even induced localized dissolution near the injection point. However, it also increases the potential release of Al, Fe and other trace metals and secondary mineral precipitation that could have an impact on water quality.

The geochemical complexities revealed in the study suggest that future research should focus on long-term geochemical evolution. In particular, monitoring should be implemented in order to assess potential secondary mineral precipitation and developing advanced mitigation strategies to maintain aquifer injectivity and system efficiency (before big issues occur). It is noteworthy that this study did not mention the biotic interaction and how high temperature injection could affect biodiversity. There is a need to incorporate these interactions as geochemical reactivity could be either enhanced or hindered by micro organism presence.

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